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Advanced lightweight materials FOR Energy-efficient Structures

D1.2 REPORT ON SUSTAINABLE CRITERIA FOR METRICS SELECTION FOR MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT AND MANUFACTURING OF BIOCOMPOSITE PARTS AND TEST-PYRAMID MATRIX DEFINITION

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
EC	European Commission
CFRP	Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites
rCF	Recycled Carbon Fibres
GF	Glass Fibres
DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
DMA	Dynamic Mechanical Analysis
LOI	Limiting Oxygen Index
DVS	Dynamic Vapour Sorption
SWA	Static Water Absorption
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
T _g	Glass Transition Temperature
ILSS	Interlaminar Shear Strength Test
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
GSM	Grams per Square Meter

1. Task Overview and Objectives

This Deliverable D1.2 corresponds to the second part of Work Package 1 of the FOREST project, in which the materials performance indicators for the sustainable composites will be defined.

As stated in the project proposal, this task is divided into two-steps: (1) state of the art of sustainable raw materials and (2) defining the metrics from the synthesis of polymers & additives and the carbon fibre recycling point of view. To complete these two steps, high-level indicators will be assessed and defined from raw material development point of view for more sustainable products: i) economic (e.g. cost of raw materials, current and future market demand), ii) environmental (e.g. availability of biobased sources for the synthesis of new chemistries for matrices and additives as well as of carbon fibre waste to ensure supply chain and have a wide variety and volume of sustainable feedstocks), iii) social & safety (e.g. sizing agent treatment compatible with recycled carbon fibres and biocomposite interfacial adhesion and the added value of biobased fire retardant products for advanced properties in the composite will be considered). Such reported metrics will constitute the roadmap for material development in WP2 at lab and higher scale and use cases definition in Task 1.4. This will be done for composites using the developed bio-benzoxazines, bio-polyacrylates and bio-polyamides. Metrics will be used for LCA method assessment in WP5. Moreover, a test-pyramid will be defined to characterise and validate material properties at coupon and prototype level.

2. Scopus and Approach

The definition of materials performance indicators for the sustainable composite development is based on a sustainability assessment focusing on the evaluation of economic, environmental as well as social and safety aspects along the different product development stages. As part of task 1.2 it shall be used to enable an effective pre-selection of raw materials and processes for the development of polymers and additives used in biocomposites in alignment with the FOREST project goals. The method was developed to reduce the effort of conventional sustainability assessments while still ensure a sufficient material and process selection in the light of sustainability. It further is meant to contribute to a consistent and continuous evaluation process and help to identify potential solutions to meet the project requirements, minimize environmental impacts, and promote sustainable practices throughout the material development process.

Even though related to an established conventional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), it is important to clarify that the developed method follows a different approach and is not intended to replace such. The LCA is a standardised method and defined in the ISO 14040 and renewed in the ISO 14044. The classical approach of an LCA is shown in Figure 1 (A). It is a quantitative method consisting of three main steps – an extensive data collection known as the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), followed by the modelling and simulation using LCA-software leading to the calculation of the environmental impact of the product in different impact categories (e. g. greenhouse gas emissions, energy consumption, water usage, waste generation, impacts on human health and ecosystems). Although this method involves a lot of effort, diligence and it is not easy to apply without further knowledge, it provides a high degree of accuracy in assessing the sustainability of the products evaluated. This also highlights the problems when it comes to the sustainability assessment at the material development entry level. At this stage there is often a lack of time and sufficient well-grounded data at hand to follow the high standards of such method. The alternative approach developed at IFAM therefore tries to compensate for this and mediates between the LCA and the material development perspectives at laboratory level. It emphasises to streamline the procedure and reduce complexity. The new method is inspired by the SURF-UK sustainability framework for remediation and illustrated in Figure 1 (B) (Bardos et al. 2018). The method adopts a "top-down" approach to the conventional product

assessment. A “potential solution” for the material development derives from the “room of potential” which generally expands with the quality of sustainability and performance. In contrast to the extensive LCI, the following method employs an evaluation cascade starting at the entry level with comparatively less effort guided by the “expert filter”. This filter describes the sustainable management for the product development, combining “general good practices” with the “expertise” of the involved developers. By combining these elements, the assessment incorporates existing knowledge and professional insights into sustainable practices. This filter therefore relies on the know-how of the experts for the material development (e. g. chemists, engineers) as well as their awareness of the project goals, market restrictions and social competences. As this approach requires an interdisciplinary understanding and is expected to be reproducible, the decision finding is complemented by the introduction of a semi-quantitative sustainable assessment framework, which will be further explained in section 5.2. Based on this framework different solutions can already be selected and further characterized and evaluated according to the testing cascades at coupon and prototype level (see section 6). The subsequent execution of a life cycle assessment, which is not part of this task, will be reserved for the final product variants and is done by the project partner ANGAZ as part of Work Package 5.

FIGURE 1: (A) SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE CONVENTIONAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT METHOD AND (B) OF THE ALTERNATIVE APPROACH AS DEVELOPED AT IFAM.

To support the identification of “hot spots” regarding the sustainability related aspects of the material development, another effective tool, the process visualisation, is used (see section 5.1).

3. State of the Art of sustainable raw materials

In the FOREST project, innovative biobased polymers and additives are combined with recycled carbon fibers to develop high-quality composite materials. As stated in the proposal, the FOREST project proposes a combination of three key-drivers for the future of the transport sector decarbonization: Reduce, Recovery, Reshape. The “renewable-carbon-approach” of the project to use existing carbon source in the form of rCF and biobased raw materials instead of fossil materials to develop new high-performance materials is a key aspect for the successful implementation of the objectives.

The biocomposite products market already has been identified as a lead market by the European Commission (EC). However, there is an urgent need to foster the development of new biopolymers to face the economic, environmental and social challenges of current state of the art materials (European Commission, 2020a). The following paragraphs present shortly the state of the art of the different raw materials as explained in the proposal.

Additionally, the state of the art of the raw materials is within the scope of the assessment method applied and used to evaluate the performance of the newly developed polymeric materials in comparison to the existing material choices. The integration of this is further explained in section 5.2 as part of the “range of potential”.

3.1 Bio-polyacrylates

Elium is a thermoplastic reactive resin based on acrylic petrol chemistry. The product is commercially available. The main advantage using Elium resins in the composite industry is the fact that all processes used with Elium are already developed – including the ones in the FOREST project

(stamping, compression moulding, pultrusion) and others (infusion and RTM). However, no biobased Elium version exists in the market so far.

3.2 Bio-polyamides

Polyamides are semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymers. They are also able to cope with high temperatures, making them interesting materials for structural applications. Bio-polyamides are known since the mid of last century and meanwhile established in many applications (Kyulavska et al., 2019). Commercially, most important are PA 11 (Rilsan®, distributed by Arkema) – a 100 % bio-derived polyamide from castor oil – and the PA x.10 types, mainly 6.10, 10.10 and the 10.12 (Vestamid® from Evonik, Germany, and EcoPA® from DSM). Also, PA 12 is a commercial biobased product that has the potential to substitute the petrol-based product. There is a huge variety of bio-derived monomers that are applied to synthesize polyamides – most of them are of academic interest and in the proof-of-concept phase (Winnacker & Rieger, 2016). The structural diversity on monomer level (intermolecular interactions) leads to partly modified properties compared to conventional, fossil-based polyamides. However, expensive synthesis routes to biobased monomers could lead to significant higher cost of bio-polyamides and therefore niche applications for respective materials.

3.3 Bio-benzoxazines

For the benzoxazine synthesis, phenolic, amines and formaldehydes can be obtained from conventional petroleum-based or renewable raw materials. Bitrez Ltd. develops the only commercially available biobased benzoxazine, produced from cardanol as a by-product from cashew nuts (United Kingdom Patent Application No. 2112469.8). Other bio-sources for phenolic monomers can be guaiacol from guaiac, eugenol occurring in clove oil, vanillin from vanilla, sesamol from sesame and phloretic acid which is obtainable from cinnamon. Furthermore, biobased isosorbide-based amine, furfuryl- or stearyl amin were investigated for the preparation of benzoxazine monomers already. Small scale sample sizes of these monomers show a variety of good thermal and high degradation temperatures exceeding 415°C for a 10% of mass loss and thermo-

mechanical properties with glass transition temperatures above 200°C compared to 150°C for conventional benzoxazine systems. (Bonnaud et al., 2019; Haubold et al., 2021) However, previously mentioned monomers show a variety of different challenges preventing the industrial upscaling or usage thereof. Biobased phenolic components exhibit easy degradable side groups leading to decomposition and pores in cured samples (guaiacol, sesamol, eugenol); a high aromaticity with reactive functions led to a short manufacturing range (DPA); long aliphatic chains led to flexible polymers that have low FST properties (cardanol) or the availability and price is reducing the industrial feasibility (magnolol, resveratrol). Also, furfurylamine showed with its high reactivity difficulties for the upscaling process. These dares can be addressed by varying and finding new combination of reactants or using a copolymer-based system.

3.4 Biobased Fire Retardants

Inorganic compounds such as phosphorous and nitrogen or aluminum hydroxide and magnesium hydroxide are the halogen free alternative to conventional flame retardants. These additives are effective when introduced in high amounts (around 50-60% w/w) but have a negative effect on the mechanical properties of the polymer. Phosphorous-based flame retardants and their combinations with nitrogen compounds to generate intumescent systems are the most effective halogen-free solution up to date with addition percentages between 20-25% w/w. But it could also be interesting for conventional oil-based polymers as an alternative to flame retardants from fossil raw materials. Focusing on fossil based phosphorous as flame retardant could become a problem for Europe as it is considered a critical raw material (European Commission, 2020b). Biomass chemical composition include carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and phosphorous which can alternatively improve the flame-retardant effect of polymers (Vassilev et al., 2010). Four main families of compounds are candidates for flame retardant applications: carbohydrates, proteins, lipids and phenolic compounds. Some of the most interesting compounds regarding the state of art are phytic acid from plant seeds (28% of phosphorous in the structure and reactive -OH groups), Chitosan from crustaceans (polysaccharide backbone with -OH and NH₂ groups), deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) (high content of nitrogen and phosphate groups) and phenolic compounds like lignin or tannins. The basic criteria to select the proper flame-retardant material is the thermal stability: the decomposition temperature of the

compound must be high enough to withstand polymer processing temperatures, high charring ability, presence of reactive chemical groups such as hydroxyl, carboxylic acid, amine or double bonds and presence of phosphorous, nitrogen or silicon with flame retardant properties.

3.5 Recycled Carbon Fibres

The use of carbon fibre in fibre reinforced composites (CFRP) is still increasing and reaches over a wide range of industries such as air, land, and sea vehicles, wind turbines, storage tanks, and sports equipment. The highest amounts of fibres are used in aerospace and for wind turbines, both sectors together are accounting for almost half of the yearly virgin fibre usage of around 117 kilotons (2022). By 2025, around 20 kilotons of carbon fibre waste will be generated annually. Thereby approximately 40% of CFRP waste already is generated during the manufacturing stage. (Zhang et al. 2020)

With the increased use of CFRP in aviation within the recent years, in this sector alone an estimated value of 23 kilotons per year of CFRP waste will be accumulated if left unrecycled by 2035 and the overall CFRP waste will cumulate to around 62 kilotons per year (Amaechi et al., 2019; Karuppanan Gopalraj & Kärki, 2020). Carbon fibers are produced from fossil raw materials requiring large amounts of energy and resources. This makes it even more important to handle them responsibly and use them efficiently as a material or resource. In addition to the before stated numbers, this illustrates the urgency of innovating and further developing recycling concepts for carbon fibre composite materials. In the UK, 35 % of carbon fibres and 67 % of glass fibres (GF) used are still sent to landfill as of today. Only 20 % of CF and 13 % of GF are recycled and 2 % of CF and 6 % of GF are reused (Karuppanan Gopalraj & Kärki, 2020). With this said, at national level, four countries have already banned the landfilling and incineration of composites by law. These countries are Germany, Austria, the Netherlands and Finland. In Germany, a law banning the direct landfilling of waste with an organic content above 5 % has been in force since 2009 (Chatziparaskeva et al., 2022). Also, it is known that rCF have a significantly lower environmental impact and energy usage when compared to virgin CF (Pillain et al, 2019). These facts highlight the need for further development of CF recycling concepts and the development of high-performance materials from recycled carbon fibres.

4. High-level sustainability indicators

Since sustainability relates to the three pillars of economy, environment and social aspects, the assessment has to be conducted based on a suitable selection of relevant sustainability indicators of each category. Such indicators are essential to measure, assess and identify, both quantitatively and qualitatively, the goals within the scope of the FOREST project regarding sustainable material developments.

The task 1.2 involves the definition of high-level sustainability indicators from raw material development point of view to achieve more sustainable products. These indicators are generally defining sustainability in the respective category (Mesa et al. 2018, Denčić-Mihajlov & Zeranski 2018, Bardos et al. 2020). For the developed assessment method, first all relevant indicators were selected. In the next step a further selection of most relevant indicators was chosen by each project partner involved in the raw material selection for the development process. For the described method, these indicators will be used to enable the traceability of the sustainability assessment of the material requirements specified in section 5.2.

The following Table 1 lists the high-level indicators. In Table 2 the further selected most relevant indicators specific for each partner are presented.

TABLE 1: SELECTION OF RELEVANT SUSTAINABILITY INDICATORS.

economic	environmental	social & safety
processability	natural resource depletion	educational potential
direct economic costs	Emissions to air	consumer awareness
direct economic benefits	land use	education, training, jobs
indirect economic costs	freshwater use	human health and safety
indirect economic benefits	environmental pollution (soil, ground and surface water)	ethics, equity, social justice
degree of innovation	biodiversity	locality (and community involvement)
employment potential	waste generation & management	
addition of value	ecology	
Consumer expenditure	availability of biobased sources	
process and production efficiency		
energy consumption		
transport		
current and future market demand		

TABLE 2: FURTHER SELECTION OF MOST RELEVANT SUSTAINABILITY INDICATORS BY ALL PARTNERS IN THE RESPECTIVE CATEGORIES.

most relevant indicators - economic					
IFAM & Bitrez & Arkema	BASF	Clariant & Aimplas	Gen2Carbon	Stelia Composites	MBT
direct & indirect costs / economic benefits					
degree of innovation & addition of value					
production efficiency & processability					
energy consumption					
current & future market demand					

transport	transport	transport	transport		
	employment potential	employment potential	employment potential		
most relevant indicators - environmental					
IFAM & Bitrez & Arkema	BASF	Clariant & Aimplas	Gen2Carbon	Stelia Composites	MBT
natural resource depletion	natural resource depletion	natural resource depletion	natural resource depletion	natural resource depletion	natural resource depletion
Emissions to air	Emissions to air	Emissions to air	Emissions to air	Emissions to air	Emissions to air
land use	land use	land use	waste generation & management	land use	land use
freshwater use	freshwater use	freshwater use		freshwater use	freshwater use
environmental pollution (soil, ground and surface water)	environmental pollution (soil, ground and surface water)	ecology & biodiversity		waste generation & management	waste generation & management
ecology & biodiversity	ecology & biodiversity	availability of biobased sources			
waste generation & management	waste generation & management				
availability of biobased sources					
most relevant indicators - Social & Safety					
IFAM & Bitrez & Arkema	BASF	Clariant & Aimplas	Gen2Carbon	Stelia Composites	MBT
education, training, jobs	education, training, jobs	human health and safety	education, training, jobs	human health and safety	human health and safety
human health and safety	human health and safety	ethics, equity, social justice	human health and safety		
ethics, equity, social justice	ethics, equity, social justice	locality (and community involvement)			
locality (and community involvement)	locality (and community involvement)				

5. Efficient evaluation of potential solutions from development perspective

After the selection of high-level sustainability indicators, the second objective of task 1.2 is the implementation of an efficient method to evaluate different raw materials for the product development. Beyond that, this method is supposed to constitute the roadmap for the material development in the following work packages at lab and higher scale-up level and use cases definition. To do this kind of assessment, first the process visualisation will be presented as a starting point, followed by the semi-quantitative assessment method.

5.1 Process Visualisation

The process visualisation is a powerful tool to improve the understanding and mapping of the product development system. It can help to gain a holistic overview of the process and to simplify complex information. All relevant steps and inputs involved can be easily identified. It means therefore a great advantage for the requirements of the analysis in terms of interdisciplinarity. This tool can be used not only for the material development at laboratory level, but also along all the other product life stages up to and including the use phase and the end-of-life. As an example, Figure 2 shows a graphical representation of the process flow of a biocomposite part made from a bio-benzoxazine matrix system and recycled carbon fibre fabric. It shows the process from “cradle-to-grave”, which includes the synthesis of the resin system, the production of the reinforcing fibre fabrics, the composite manufacturing, part assembly up to the use phase and the end-of-life. It further marks the system boundary and identifies the main inputs and output.

5.2 Semi-quantitative Assessment Method

The aim of the semi-quantitative assessment method is to effectively evaluate different feedstocks with respect to the defined product and process requirements in alignment with the FOREST project goals. As this needs to be understood as a continuous and holistic approach, this template is designed to cover the scope of the whole material development requirements, from raw materials to composite to the end-of-life. It can therefore be used as a helpful tool to track the performance of different material solutions throughout the project, not only in the light of sustainability but also in comparison to conventional materials.

In Table 3 and Table 4, the process and product specific requirements of each polymer, as well as the fire-retardant additives, the recycled carbon fibres and the composite requirements from the manufacturer perspective are listed.

TABLE 3: PROCESS AND PRODUCT SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS OF THE DEVELOPED POLYMERS WITH THEIR RESPECTIVE WEIGHTS ACCORDING TO DEVELOPER AND MANUFACTURER PERSPECTIVE.

<i>Main Product</i>	Process / Sub-Product	Process/Product-specific requirements	weight
Bio-benzoxazines (IFAM & Bitrez)	Synthesis	low use of auxiliary materials	5%
		good local availability of raw materials	5%
		high process scalability (per reaction)	15%
		low energy intensive process (temperature, time, ...)	10%
		high yield of educt	15%
		low volatile generation during synthesis	5%
		low price of raw materials (plant material)	5%
		high mass availability of raw materials (educts/reactants)	15%
		recyclability of solvents	5%
		high bio-content	20%
		100 %	
<i>(IFAM & Bitrez)</i>	Uncured system	high resin bio-content	20%
		high pot-life	5 %
		high shelf-life	10 %
		high compatibility with rCF (chemical, physical wettability)	5 %
		high compatibility with sizing polymer	5 %
		high compatibility with additive	5 %
		short time curing cycles (high reactivity)	10 %
		low curing on-set temperature	10 %
		low melting point	5 %
		low odor nuisance	5 %
		low toxicity	10 %
		low viscosity	5 %
		low shrinkage	5 %
		100 %	
<i>(IFAM & Bitrez)</i>	Cured system	high thermal stability	10 %
		high chemical stability	5 %
		low moisture sensitivity	5 %
		high Tg	15 %
		good adhesion to fibre	15 %
		high stiffness	10 %
		high strength	10 %
		high ductility	10 %

**Bio-
polyamides**
(BASF)

	low use of (fire) additives	5 %
	good compatibility with (fire) additives	5 %
	low flammability	10 %
	low porosity	10 %
		100 %

Synthesis	low use of auxiliary materials	5 %
	good local availability of raw materials (monomers)	10 %
	high process scalability (per reaction)	15 %
	low energy intensive process (temperature, time, ...)	10 %
	high yield of educt	15 %
	low volatile generation during synthesis	5 %
	low price of raw materials (plant material)	5 %
	high mass availability of raw materials (educts/reactants)	15 %
	high bio-content	30 %
		100 %

Cured system	high thermal stability	15 %
	high Tg	15 %
	good adhesion to fibre	15 %
	good compatibility with additives (including FR additive)	15 %
	tuned rheology for pultrusion process	15 %
	high strength	10 %
	high stiffness	10 %
	high ductility	5 %
		100 %

**Bio-
polyacrylates**
(Arkema)

Synthesis	low use of auxiliary materials	5 %
	good local availability of raw materials (monomers)	5 %
	high process scalability (per reaction)	15 %
	low energy intensive process (temperature, time, ...)	10 %
	high yield of educt	15 %
	low volatile generation during synthesis	5 %
	low price of raw materials (plant material)	5 %
	high mass availability of raw materials (educts/reactants)	15 %
	high bio-content	10 %
	recyclability of solvents	15 %
		100 %

TABLE 4: PROCESS AND PRODUCT SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS OF THE USED MATERIALS ACCORDING TO DEVELOPER AND MANUFACTURER PERSPECTIVE.

Main Product	Process / Sub-Product	Process/Product-specific requirements	weight
Additives (IFAM)	Fire	high bio-content	20 %
		Retardant	high compatibility with Biobenzoxazine
	high compatibility with rCF		5 %
	high compatibility with sizing polymer		5 %
	good fire-retardant properties		20 %
	good local availability		5 %
	high mass availability		5 %
	low energy intensive synthesis		15 %
	low price	10 %	
		100 %	
<i>(Aimplas & Clariant)</i>	Fire	high bio-content	25 %
	Retardant	high processability	20 %
	PEC	good compatibility with bio-polyamides	10 %
		good fire retarding properties	20 %
		high mass availability	15 %
		low cost	10 %
		100 %	
Fibres (Gen2Carbon)	Recycled Carbon	low energy intensive recovery process	20 %
		high stiffness	10 %
	Fibres	high strength	10 %
		low moisture sensitivity	5 %
		high compatibility with Bio-benzoxazine	5 %
		high compatibility with Additives	5 %
		high compatibility with sizing polymers	5 %
		homogeneous surface structure	10 %
		low price	15 %
		homogeneous fibre length and diameter	5 %
		good local availability	5 %
		high mass availability of feedstock (recyclable CF-parts)	5 %
<i>(Gen2Carbon)</i>		high homogeneity (fibre distribution, gsm, fibre length, thickness)	30 %

	Recycled	good wettability with bio-benzoxazines	10 %
	Carbon Fibre	low hairiness	10 %
	Fabrics	fibre alignment / orientation	5 %
		low moisture sensitivity	5 %
		low energy intensive production process	15 %
		low price	15 %
		good drapeability	10 %
		100 %	
Composite <i>(Stelia Composites)</i>	Composite	high specific strength	10 %
		high specific stiffness	5 %
		low density	10 %
		low porosity	10 %
		low moisture sensitivity	5 %
		good mechanical workability	10 %
		high thermal stability	5 %
		low toxicity	5 %
		high chemical resistance	5 %
		low pressure production process	5 %
		low energy intensive production process	5 %
		high bio-content	15 %
		recyclability of parts	10 %
		100 %	
<i>(MBT)</i>	Composite	high specific strength	10 %
		low density	15 %
		high thermal stability	15 %
		low toxicity	10 %
		coating ability	15 %
		good adhesion to BiW	15 %
		high bio-content	5 %
		recyclability of parts	15 %
		100 %	
<i>(Stellantis)</i>	Composite		
			100 %

The overview of the assessment Excel-file is shown in Table 5 (part 1) and Table 6 (part 2) exemplary for the bio-benzoxazine development at IFAM and Bitrez. This table is used to pre-define the material and process selection in terms of sustainability. It is meant to enable a mainly qualitative, rather than quantitative comparison of different product specific solutions. This approach allows for an efficient requirement-based pre-selection as stated in task 1.2. In the following the assessment method using the Excel-file is described.

After the definition of sustainable criteria and the metrics selection for each main product or process from development and manufacturing perspectives, the respective requirements weights will be determined. This represents the importance of each requirement and will offer an opportunity to tailor and adjust the evaluation method to the project objectives. In the next column of Table 5 the related sustainability indicators for each requirement will be allocated. These indicators are taken from Table 1. This allows for the calculation of the “sustainability share”, which represents the ratio of the three pillars of sustainability (economical, environmental, social & safety) from the distribution of the sustainability indicators for the respective product or process. In the example this leads to the conclusion, that the assessment of the synthesis of bio-benzoxazines is mostly based on economic considerations (45 %), followed by environmental (36 %) and is the least evaluated by social & safety concerns (11 %). The next part of the excel sheet, shown in the left part of Table 6, defines the “range of potential” giving the “performance goal” (how good does it have to be) and the “state of the art” (how good is it). The performance goal should quantify the ideal (but realistic) goal of the respective requirement. This approach is used to express in numbers how much room for potential development there is for each requirement. It can therefore be helpful for the next step, the evaluation of potential solutions, to know where each solution falls within this range. Depending on this, for this last part of the excel sheet, shown in the right part of Table 6, a potential solution will be rated from 1 to 5 (bad to good). The respective value can be multiplied with the before determined requirement weight to calculate the overall score of the potential solution with respect to the sustainable criteria and metrics selection. In the example, gallic acid appears to be the most promising candidate so far as feedstock for the phenol species for the benzoxazine synthesis. According to the holistic and continuous approach of the method, this will be applied to the different product-specific hierarchy levels along the product development (e. g. other biopolymers, additives, recycled carbon fibres and composites).

TABLE 5: PART 1 OF THE OVERVIEW OF THE ASSESSMENT EXCEL-FILE AND THE RESPECTIVE INPUTS BY THE EXAMPLE OF THE BIO-BENZOXAZINE SYNTHESIS AT IFAM SHOWING THE RESULTING “SUSTAINABILITY SHARE” OF THE SELECTED REQUIREMENTS.

Main Product	Process / Sub-Product	Process/Product-specific requirements	weight	Sustainability Indicating Requirements	Sustainability Share					
					economic		environmental		social & safety	
					relative	overall	relative	overall	relative	overall
BIO-BENZOXAZINE	Synthesis	low use of auxiliary materials	5%	direct & indirect costs production efficiency & processability waste generation & management natural resource depletion transport	50%	5%	50%	5%	0%	0%
		good local availability of raw materials	5%	current & future market demand Emissions to air ecology & biodiversity freshwater use education, training, jobs locality (and community involvement)	29%	5%	43%	7%	29%	5%
		high process scalability (per reaction)	15%	current & future market demand production efficiency & processability availability of biobased sources	67%	5%	33%	2%	0%	0%
		low energy intensive process	10%	energy consumption Emissions to air	50%	2%	50%	2%	0%	0%
		high yield of educt	15%	direct & indirect costs degree of innovation & addition of value production efficiency & processability energy consumption natural resource depletion waste generation & management	67%	9%	33%	5%	0%	0%
		low volatile generation during	5%	production efficiency & processability human health and safety	50%	2%	0%	0%	50%	2%
		low price of raw materials (plant material)	5%	direct & indirect costs current & future market demand degree of innovation & addition of value ethics, equity, social justice	75%	7%	0%	0%	25%	2%
		high mass availability of raw materials (educts/reactants)	15%	current & future market demand production efficiency & processability natural resource depletion availability of biobased sources ecology & biodiversity locality (and community involvement)	33%	5%	50%	7%	17%	2%
		recyclability of solvents	5%	direct & indirect costs production efficiency & processability natural resource depletion degree of innovation & addition of value	67%	5%	33%	2%	0%	0%
		high bio-content	20%	natural resource depletion land use freshwater use	25%	2%	75%	7%	0%	0%
		Sum	100%			45%		36%		11%

TABLE 6: PART 2 OF THE OVERVIEW OF THE ASSESSMENT EXCEL-FILE AND THE RESPECTIVE INPUTS BY THE EXAMPLE OF THE BIO-BENZOXAZINE SYNTHESIS AT IFAM SHOWING THE “RANGE OF POTENTIAL” AND THE RESULTING SCORE OF DIFFERENT EVALUATED PHENOL FEEDSTOCKS.

Performance - Goal	Range of Potential			Rating of potential Solution (1-5 = bad-good)										
	Quantification (if applicable)	Unit	Performance - State of the Quantification (if applicable)	Unit	Gallic acid		P-hydroxybenzoic acid		Phloretic acid		Catechol		Pyrogallol	
					absolute	weighted	absolute	weighted	absolute	weighted	absolute	weighted	absolute	weighted
0	kg	0,1	kg	4,0	0,2	4,0	0,2	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	4,0	2,0	
1000	km	4000-8000 km (Cardanol - Mali/India)	km	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	
100	kg	2,0	kg	2,5	0,4	2,5	0,4	4,0	0,6	2,5	0,4	2,5	0,4	
Gideon	kJ		kJ	4,0	0,4	2,0	0,2	2,5	0,3	2,5	0,3	3,5	0,4	
90 (BASF)	%	70,0	%	3,0	0,5	3,0	0,5	4,0	0,6	2,5	0,4	2,5	0,4	
0	L	0,1	L	3,0	0,2	4,0	0,2	4,0	0,2	4,0	0,2	3,0	0,2	
1 (Priamin)	Euro /100 g	226 (Cardanol)	Euro/100g	4,0	0,2	5,0	0,3	3,0	0,2	5,0	0,3	3,0	0,2	
70	kt/year	37,0	kt/year (Cardanol)	3,0	0,5	4,0	0,6	3,0	0,5	3,0	0,5	2,5	0,4	
100	%		%	3,0	0,2	3,0	0,2	5,0	0,3	2,5	0,1	2,5	0,1	
100	%	70,0	%	4,0	0,8	4,0	0,8	4,0	0,8	4,0	0,8	3,5	0,7	
Score				33,00	5,68	34,00	5,73	36,00	9,80	32,50	7,33	29,50	7,10	

6. Test Cascades at Coupon Level

The evaluation and characterisation of the materials properties of the newly developed materials can be generally divided into the following three hierarchy levels of testing – the raw material level, including the neat polymer systems in an uncured and cured state as well as the recycled carbon fibres and textiles, the modified material with additives including fire retardant additives, and the composite level (see Figure 3). The respective test cascade is presented in Table 7.

FIGURE 3 : THE THREE HIERARCHY LEVELS OF TESTING THE MATERIALS AT COUPON LEVEL.

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW OF THE DIFFERENT OBJECTIVES AND PLANNED TEST METHODS TO CHARACTERISE AND EVALUATE THE DEVELOPED MATERIALS ON THE RESPECTIVE LEVELS ACCORDING TO FIGURE 3.

<i>Material Level</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Test</i>
<i>Recycled Carbon Fibres</i>	Mechanical properties	Single fibre tensile test
	Fibre structure and shape, Surface properties	Optical methods (SEM, Microscopy)
<i>Recycled Carbon Fibre Fabrics</i>	Fabric structure and shape, Fibre orientation, Surface properties	Optical methods (SEM, Microscopy)
	Mechanical properties	Tensile test
	Moisture sensitivity wettability	Moisture analysis Wettability tests
<i>Uncured Biopolymer Systems</i>	Processing properties	Rheology / Viscometry
	Storage & processing constrains (Shelf Life, Pot life)	Rheology / Viscometry
	Thermal properties (polymerisation / curing, thermal degradation)	DSC, TGA
<i>Cured Biopolymer Systems</i>	Curing cycles for pure matrix systems	DSC
	Melting point & Tg	DSC, DMA
	Degree of crystallinity	DSC
	Thermal Degradation	TGA
	Thermal conductivity	Thermography
	Mechanical properties	Tensile Test (ISO 527), DMA
	Fire retardancy	UL 94, LOI Test, ISO 5660-1
	Moisture sensitivity	DVS
<i>Composites</i>	Curing cycles for composites	DSC
	Fibre-Matrix Interaction (Wettability)	Contact angle measurements

Chemical Nature	FTIR
Morphological Analysis	SEM
Degree of crystallinity	DSC
Thermal Degradation	TGA
Thermal conductivity	Thermography
Mechanical properties	Tensile Test (ISO 527), DMA, Flexural Test (ISO 14125), Interlaminar Shear Strength Test (ILSS), Impact Test (ISO 179), Adhesion (ASTM D4541)
Fire retardancy	ISO 2685, UL 94, LOI Test (ASTM E2863), ISO 5660-1, ASTM E1354, Thermal Runway Test, ISO 3795, FMVSS 302,
Moisture sensitivity	DVS, SWA (ISO 62)
Electromagnetic Shielding Effectiveness	ASTM D4935-10

For the evaluation of the biocomposites coupons at laboratory level, depending on the application with respect to the use cases and specific requirements, different emphasis is put on the material development and testing. For the bus roof covering panel, high strength and stiffness as well as fire resistance (according to ISO 3795 and FMVSS 302) are most important aspects. For the cockpit ceiling panel and the battery cover panel, additionally the electromagnetic shielding effectiveness (EMI) is of high importance. Also, according to the use case, different test standards to evaluate the fire resistance will be applied. For the cockpit panel, the fire resistance will be tested as stated in CS/FAR-25 (ISO 2685) and according to AITM 2.0002A. For the battery cover panel, next to the UL94 and LOI tests, a new test standard to evaluate the thermal runaway properties of the material will be developed from Stellantis.

7. Conclusions

The implemented approach for a sustainability assessment at an early material development stage presents a highly useful method for selecting materials on a semi-quantitative level. This method proves advantageous not just for a single stage, such as synthesis, but for all development phases throughout the project. Unlike the resource-intensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) method, this approach requires considerably fewer effort, while yielding semi-quantitative results at entry level to enable a sustainable material selection with respect to the project objectives. The test cascade provides the basis for characterising the various materials, components, and parts developed within the project.

8. Literature

Amaechi, Chiemela & Odijie, Charles & Orok, Etim & Job, Stella. (2019). Economic Aspects of Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite Recycling. 10.1016/B978-0-12-803581-8.10738-6.

Bardos, Paul & Thomas, Hayley & Smith, Jonathan & Harries, Nicola & Evans, Frank & Boyle, Richard & Howard, Trevor & Lewis, Richard & Thomas, Alan & Haslam, Angela. (2018). The Development and Use of Sustainability Criteria in SuRF-UK's Sustainable Remediation Framework. Sustainability. 10. 1781. 10.3390/su10061781.

Bardos, Paul & Thomas, Hayley & Smith, Jonathan & Harries, Nicola & Evans, Frank & Boyle, Richard & Howard, Trevor & Lewis, Richard & Thomas, Alan & Dent, Vivien & Haslam, Angela. (2021). Sustainability assessment framework and indicators developed by SuRF-UK for land remediation option appraisal. Remediation Journal. 31. 1-22. 10.1002/rem.21668.

Bonnaud, L.; Chollet, B.; Dumas, L.; Peru, A.A.M.; Flourat, A.L.; Allais, F.; Dubois, P (2019). High-Performance Bio-Based Benzoxazines from Enzymatic Synthesis of Diphenols. Macromol. Chem. Phys., 220, 1800312, doi:10.1002/macp.201800312.

Denčić-Mihajlov, Ksenija & Zeranski, Stefan. (2018). DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABILITY INDICATORS: APPROACHES, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES. *Facta Universitatis, Series: Economics and Organization*. 291. 10.22190/FUEO1704291D.

European Commission (2020a). Directorate-General for Communication, Circular Economy Action Plan: the European Green Deal, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2775/855540>

European Commission (2020b). Raw Materials Information System <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/?page=crm-list-2020-e294f6>.

Haubold, T.S.; Puchot, L.; Adjaoud, A.; Verge, P.; Koschek, K. (2021). Bio-Based Bisbenzoxazines with Flame Retardant Linker. *Polymers*, 13, doi:10.3390/polym13244330.

Karuppannan Gopalraj, S., Kärki, T. A (2020). Review on the recycling of waste carbon fibre/glass fibre-reinforced composites: fibre recovery, properties and life-cycle analysis. *SN Appl. Sci.* **2**, 433. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-2195-4>.

Kyulavska M., Toncheva-Moncheva N., Rydz J. (2019). Biobased Polyamide Ecomaterials and Their Susceptibility to Biodegradation. In: Martínez L., Kharissova O., Kharisov B. (eds) *Handbook of Ecomaterials*. Springer.

Mesa, Jaime A & Esparragoza, Ivan & Maury Ramirez, Heriberto. (2018). Developing a set of sustainability indicators for product families based on the circular economy model. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 196. 1429–1442. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.131.

Pillain, Baptiste & Loubet, Philippe & Fadri, Pestalozzi & Woidasky, Jörg & Erriguible, Arnaud & Aymonier, Cyril & Sonnemann, Guido. (2019). Positioning supercritical solvolysis among innovative recycling and current waste management scenarios for carbon fiber reinforced plastics thanks to comparative life cycle assessment. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*. 154. 104607. 10.1016/j.supflu.2019.104607.

Vassilev SV., Baxter D., Andersen LK., Vassileva CG. (2010). An overview of the chemical composition of biomass, *Fuel*, 89, 913-933.

Winnacker, M., Rieger, B. (2016). Biobased Polyamides: Recent Advances in Basic and Applied Research, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.*, 37, 1391–1413.

Zhang, Jin & Chevali, Venkata & Hao, Wang & Wang, Chun. (2020). Current status of carbon fibre and carbon fibre composites recycling. *Composites Part B: Engineering.* 193. 108053. 10.1016/j.compositesb.2020.108053.

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